

DIGITAL ECOSYSTEMS FOR SUSTAINABLE DIGITALISATION OF FARMING

Abstract

This policy brief presents insights on how digital ecosystems can foster sustainable digitalisation in European farming, based on the analysis of 19 agricultural Living Labs under the CODECS project. The analysis draws on both institutional and organisational perspectives: Ostrom's Socio-Ecological Systems Framework and the resources and capabilities approach, often used in enterprise management studies.

Key enablers and barriers shaping digital transformation across diverse agricultural contexts are identified. Findings highlight persistent challenges such as fragmented governance, limited digital skills, insufficient infrastructure, and financial constraints, alongside opportunities for innovation and collaboration. Building on this evidence, the brief outlines five policy priorities: strengthening digital ecosystem foundations; empowering human capital and knowledge systems; enabling inclusive and adaptive governance; fostering innovation and financial accessibility; and aligning digitalisation with sustainability. Together, these actions provide a roadmap for developing conducive digital ecosystems that enhance resilience, efficiency, and environmental sustainability in European agriculture.

Background and context

This Policy Brief draws on the findings of Deliverable 3.1 – Digital Ecosystem Analysis, developed within Work Package 3 (*Analysis of Digital Ecosystems*) of the CODECS project (*Maximising the co-benefits of agricultural digitalisation through conducive digital ecosystems*). The objective of this work is to analyse how agricultural digital ecosystems function across 19 Living Labs (LLs) in Europe and to identify the enabling and constraining factors that shape the sustainable digitalisation of farming.

Within CODECS, digital ecosystems (DEs) are understood as dynamic systems where digital, socio-economic, organisational, knowledge, and physical components interact to support the creation, communication, and use of digital technologies and data. Each Living Lab represents a network of farmers, knowledge intermediaries, stakeholders, policymakers, technology providers, and other concerned actors around an emerging problem within a given application scenario, and is willing to develop solutions through collaboration.

The analytical approach combines both institutional and organisational enterprise studies: (i) Elinor Ostrom's Socio-Ecological Systems Framework (SESF), which captures the complex interrelations and conceptualises ecosystems as four interconnected subsystems: actors, governance systems, resource units and resource systems, and (ii) the Resources, Capabilities, Collaborations, and Innovations (RCCIs) perspective, a core organisational studies approach for understanding how entities can respond to changing environments. This integration allows for a

systemic assessment of the conditions under which digitalisation can drive sustainability, inclusion, and resilience in farming systems, identifying assets, skills, networks and innovations that shape transitions.

The mapping of the socio-ecological contexts and digital ecosystems provide key insights into the digital ecosystem conduciveness, which refers to the extent to which the environment supports the growth, success, and adoption of digital activities, such as the development of new technologies, the creation of new businesses, and the adoption of digital solutions and farmers' digital readiness understood as the individual or organisation's ability to adapt and effectively utilise digital technologies and tools to achieve their goals and objectives. Together, these findings form the evidence base for developing policy recommendations that can enhance the sustainability and inclusiveness of agricultural digitalisation in Europe.

Conceptual framework

An important consideration in transitions to sustainability is the ecosystem context in which digitalisation occurs and how these environments enhance the capacities of farmers, advisors, businesses, and other AKIS actors in agricultural contexts.

The SESF identifies four interrelated subsystems (actors, resource units, resource systems, and governance systems) that define the enabling conditions for digitalisation, meanwhile the RCCIs perspective adds an organisational lens focusing on the tangible and intangible assets, skills, networks, and innovations required by entities for sustainable digitalisation. Within this approach, the concept of capabilities is central to understanding how digital ecosystems evolve and how actors build digital readiness. Both functional capabilities and in particular dynamic capabilities are important, the latter being understood as the ability to adapt and reconfigure resources in response to change.

Methodologically, the analysis explores how the SESF subsystems enable the provision of RCCIs required for LLs to implement their digitalisation initiatives and address their specific challenges (thus allowing exploration and definition of conducive digital ecosystems). Each LL begins by defining a clear problem statement, followed by four analytical steps:

- Step 1: Identify the current (*what they have*) and required (*what they need*) RCCIs to address their problem statement.
- Step 2: Analyse how the four SESF subsystems enable, foster, or constrain the RCCIs necessary to solve the identified challenges.
- Step 3: Use the identified RCCIs to assess digital ecosystem conduciveness and farmer digital readiness characteristics.
- Step 4: Develop indicators to characterise and compare digital ecosystems across Living Labs.

This integrated framework allows CODECS to explore how social, institutional, and technical elements combine to create or constrain digital ecosystem conduciveness ensuring that digital solutions are not only technically effective but also socially acceptable and environmentally sustainable for farming across European agricultural contexts.

Policy Implications and Recommendations

Strengthen Digital Ecosystem Foundations

Strengthening the foundations of digital ecosystems requires investing in robust rural IT infrastructure, including broadband connectivity, cloud platforms, and open data systems. Equally important is the promotion of open-source and interoperable standards, which enhance system connectivity, foster collaboration, and reduce dependency on specific technology providers.

Empower Human Capital and Knowledge Systems

Empowering human capital and strengthening knowledge systems involves expanding digital literacy and data management training within Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) to ensure all actors can engage with new technologies. Cross-sectoral learning should be encouraged through closer collaboration among farmers, advisors, researchers, and technology providers. Additionally, sustained funding for Living Labs and training farms is crucial, as these spaces enable hands-on experimentation, peer learning, and the co-creation of practical digital solutions.

Enable Inclusive and Adaptive Governance

Creating inclusive and adaptive governance frameworks requires simplifying regulations related to technology testing, such as those governing drone operations and data sharing, to make innovation more accessible. Governance models should be participatory, actively involving farmers and other stakeholders in co-design and decision-making processes. Moreover, transparency and fairness in data ownership and use must be ensured to build trust, encourage collaboration, and support equitable digital transformation across the sector.

Foster Innovation and Financial Accessibility

Fostering innovation and improving financial accessibility can be achieved by developing blended finance mechanisms and grant schemes specifically designed to support SMEs and smallholders, who often face barriers to technological adoption. Public-private partnerships should be incentivised to co-develop digital solutions tailored to local agricultural needs. Furthermore, strengthening innovation ecosystems, such as Living Labs, can enhance collaboration between agricultural and digital stakeholders, accelerating the creation and diffusion of context-appropriate technologies.

Align Digitalisation with Sustainability

Aligning digitalisation with sustainability goals involves promoting digital technologies that minimise inputs, emissions, and waste while enhancing resource efficiency across agricultural systems. Environmental performance indicators should be integrated into digitalisation programmes to monitor and guide their impact. Additionally, new business models are needed to connect data-driven innovation with sustainable principles, ensuring that digital transformation supports both productivity and ecological stewardship.

Conclusion: Towards Sustainable Digital Ecosystems in Farming

The analysis of digital ecosystems across the Living Labs reveals that sustainable digitalisation in agriculture depends on the alignment of resources, capabilities, and governance within supportive socio-ecological contexts. While digital tools and infrastructures offer great potential, persistent gaps in connectivity, financial accessibility, digital skills, and institutional coordination continue to hinder progress. The policy recommendations outlined in this document provide a roadmap for building more resilient and equitable digital ecosystems.

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